

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Temporal and spatial lengthscales in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ observations

Deliverable D5.5

OCEAN:ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

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About this document

Deliverable: D5.5 Temporal and spatial lengthscales in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ observations

Work Package: WP5 Ice sheet impacts on global ocean circulation

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

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History of changes

Version	Date	Description	Authors (A) & Reviewers (R)
1	30 April 2024	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	7 October 2024	Revision after the 1 st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The publishable summary has been expanded. 2) Integrations have been added to the methodology in section (2.1, 2.1.1, 2.1.2) 3) References have been added in section 2.1.3 4) Integrations have been added to the impact in section 3. Delivery to the European Commission.	A: Xabier Davila, Elaine McDonagh (NORCE) R: C. Bearzotti (DMI)

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1. Publishable summary

This deliverable is a report on analyses undertaken to determine the lengthscales and timescales of oxygen isotope ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) variations in the surface ocean based on observations. We find that there are multiple lengthscales, up to three (depending on the length of the segment being analysed). We characterise these lengthscales as being short (eddy) (typically 100-300km), an intermediate scale (500-700 km) and a long gyre scale (1000-1500 km). The spatial distribution of the short decorrelation lengthscales is consistent with the pervasiveness of eddies in the Southern Ocean, while longer lengthscales depict the zonal nature of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current as well as the structure of the Ross and Weddell gyres. The differences in the spatial patterns depending on whether the analysis is undertaken zonally or meridionally suggest that at the largest scales, the decorrelation lengthscales are anisotropic, with zonal lengthscales mostly featuring the circumpolar current, while northward scales indicating the northward spreading of the Subantarctic Mode Waters. Regarding the decorrelation timescales, unfortunately, while the available time series in the Southern Ocean suggest some interannual variability, the quantity of observations is not enough to characterise the temporal variability. Scales associated with oxygen isotopes are similar to those for salinity, whereas there are some differences with temperature.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

Identifying the structure of water masses, their distribution and properties, is essential for constructing an efficient observing system capable to detect the ongoing circulation changes due to enhanced melting of the Antarctica ice sheets. An efficient observing system would maximize the information gain from observational efforts while avoiding unnecessary information redundancy.

We focus on the surface ocean for two reasons,

- The near-surface ocean is where there are the most observations so we are most likely to get robust results here.
- The near-surface ocean represents the boundary condition that will be used in the rest of the work planned in this project task.

The structure of the surface ocean can be assessed by the spatiotemporal variability of different water mass properties, -i.e., how a measured property varies in time and space with respect to the same property at another location or a different time. This can be estimated by diagnosing the decorrelation length and timescales as was done for the expendable bathythermograph (XBT) data to determine the optimal spacing of Argo floats in the Argo fleet to determine upper ocean heat content. Decorrelation lengthscales indicate the lag or offset at which spatial changes in a property have zero correlation. The decorrelation lengthscales indicate the dominant lengthscales of spatial variability. Similarly, decorrelation time scales describe the lag or offset at which a timeseries has zero correlation and thus the dominant timescale.

Decorrelation scales are estimated with the Autocorrelation function (e.g. Box et al., 2015), where the sample autocorrelation coefficient, r_k , for a given lag, k , is given by:

$$r_k = \frac{c_k}{c_0} \tag{Equation 1}$$

Where c_0 is the sample variance of the series and $c_k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^{N-k} (y_t - \bar{y})(y_{t+k} - \bar{y})$. Where y_t is the spatial- or time-series, and \bar{y} is its mean. N is the number of points in the series. Figure 1 gives an example of how the decorrelation lengthscale is determined. The point where the autocorrelation value intercepts zero gives the spatial lag at which the series is decorrelated and therefore indicates the size of the structure dominating the variance of the series. Decorrelation scales were estimated for available observations of space- and time-series of temperature, salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (the ratio of Oxygen-18 to Oxygen-16). For the spatial analysis, decorrelation length-scales were calculated for the northward, southward, eastward and westward directions.

Fig.1: Spatial autocorrelation of a small section in the Southern Ocean.

Fig.2: Dependency of westward decorrelation lengthscales and the chosen length of the spatial series for a spatial array starting at 51°S and 163°W.

2.1.1 Decorrelation lengthscales

The decorrelation lengthscales were calculated from state estimate fields of these properties from the Total Matrix Intercomparison (TMI) (Gebbie & Huybers, 2010a). The TMI is a data-based transport matrix where a steady-state ocean circulation is constrained using climatological observations of different tracers (temperature, salinity, nitrate, phosphate, oxygen and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$).

Fig.3: Eastward decorrelation lengthscales estimated from spatial series of different length in the Southern Ocean.

The climatological observations of temperature, salinity, nitrate, phosphate and oxygen that Gebbie & Huybers (2010a) used to constrain the TMI are taken from the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) gridded climatology by Gouretski & Koltermann (2004). More relevant for this piece of work, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ observations ingested in the TMI are taken from LeGrande & Schmidt (2006) which are based on individual $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ from NASA-GISS dataset (Schmidt et al., 1999) that were gridded using regional Salinity - $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ relationships and water mass properties. The inversion used in the TMI seeks for the mass fluxes among neighboring gridcells that explain the tracer fields within their uncertainty. The optimal solution provides adjusted tracer fields that are consistent with each other and the derived ocean circulation field. The resulting tracer fields (and circulation) is a state estimate that is representative of the modern ocean circulation (Gebbie & Huybers, 2010a). The state tracer fields have a resolution of $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ and 33 depth levels (of which only surface is analysed here), and are available at Gebbie et al. (2023) and GitHub (<https://github.com/ggebbie/TMI.jl>).

We found a dependence between the decorrelation lengthscale calculated from the autocorrelation and the length of the spatial series (Figure 2 and 3). This is possible because the auto correlation coefficient (r_k in Equation 1) is dependent on the variance of the series (c_0 in Equation 1). If the characteristic magnitude (size of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signature) of long features is larger than small or intermediate features, then these dominate when the length of the analysed series exceeds the lengthscale of the long features. When the length of the analysed series is similar to the short lengthscale, the series variance and autocorrelation coefficient is dominated by this short lengthscale. If the smallest lengthscale features had the largest magnitude then they would dominate the series variance and autocorrelation coefficient regardless of the length of the series, we generally do not find that to be the case.

In general, the shorter the spatial series, the shorter the decorrelation lengthscale, and thus, the smaller the structure that is represented. However, this relationship breaks at given lengthscales for a few iterations where the length of the spatial series is increased but the decorrelation scale stays relatively constant (e.g., between 30 and 46° in Figure 2). From these “staircases”, we infer three different categories which are representative of the size of the sampled structures: “small”, “medium” and “large”. At “small” spatial series of few degrees (few hundreds of kilometers), the decorrelation lengthscales are of about 250 km. These decorrelation lengthscales are in agreement with those estimated from Argo of <400 km (Ninove et al., 2016). At these lengthscales, the structures are typically categorized as mesoscale eddies, however in the Southern Ocean the eddy lengthscale is shorter than this and it is unclear what dynamical feature this shorter lengthscale relates to. The eddy lengthscale of high latitudes is close to the resolution of the product used so we would not expect eddies to be well represented. An analysis of these eddy lengthscales would require a higher spatial resolution data set that was not available. For longer spatial series, 50-100°, decorrelation lengthscales typically increase to 500-2000 km, and feature the presence of small gyres. At even larger spatial series, the identified structures correspond to large scale gyres. The size of such coherent structures identified by the decorrelation length-scales offer guidance to future sampling efforts. As such, the spatial frequency of the sampling highly depends on the size of the water mass feature that is intended to be observed, the larger the water masses, the smaller the spatial frequency can be, and vice versa.

Fig.4: Westward “small” decorrelation lengthscales for surface temperature, salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in kilometres. The colour-scale indicates the distance at which the spatial series is correlated with the meridional data series.

We attempted to make maps of decorrelation lengthscale using an automatic detection algorithm (Figure 4,5,6). The algorithm classifies the lengthscales according to changes in the decorrelation lengthscales tendency against changes in the length of the spatial series. Each step of the staircase in Figure 2 is defined as a water mass structure. Where the tendency changes with respect the “flatter”

Fig.5: Same as Figure 4 but for the “medium” lengthscales.

section, marks the characteristic decorrelation lengthscale or the size of the water mass structure. The algorithm worked, but not everywhere, as in some cases these staircases were not well captured automatically and thus this criterion is not always fulfilled, which is why there are white gaps in the decorrelation lengthscale maps. Further work would be required to refine the automatic detection algorithm.

The ubiquity of “small” decorrelation lengthscales when using short spatial series is consistent with the pervasiveness of small scale features in the Southern Ocean (Figure 3 and 4). This agrees well with our understanding of eddies in the Southern Ocean, although the lengthscales identified here are an order of magnitude larger than what previous observations suggest (Sallée et al., 2008). The eastward decorrelation lengthscales (not shown) are similar to the westwards lengthscales.

The larger the lengthscale, the larger are the water mass structure identified. Westward lengthscales are coherent with the meridional flow of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, where decorrelation lengthscales reach up to 1400 km (Figure 5). The eastward lengthscales also depict the Circumpolar Current (not shown) similar to the westward lengthscales. At even larger lengthscale (“large” lengthscales), we identify the Ross and Weddell gyre as covarying structures in terms of temperature, salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Figure 6). Decorrelation lengthscales are greater in the Ross gyre than in the Weddell gyre. In general, the similarities between the decorrelation lengthscales of salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ highlight the tight relationship between $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and salinity, which are equally impacted by the meteoric water (meteorological precipitation). While processes that add/remove meteoric water are likely the main reason for the similar lengthscales for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and salinity, note that the gridded $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ fields that the TMI uses already has implicit relationships with salinity (LeGrande & Schmidt, 2006), and therefore local process that affect $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and salinity differently (e.g., sea ice melting/formation) are not well represented. Temperature is typically correlated on longer lengthscales (than salinity and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) for both the Ross and Weddell gyre. It is worth noting that these lengthscales are estimated from a state estimate, whereas in reality, temporal variability might alter this regional spatial correlation.

Fig.6: Same as Figure 4 but for “large” northward lengthscales.

At “medium” and “large” scales the decorrelation lengthscales are anisotropic – i.e., the northwards decorrelation lengthscales are typically larger and clearly depict the Ross and Weddell gyre structure. Meridional lengthscales, primarily feature the Antarctic Circumpolar Current.

We do not make a formal estimate of uncertainty on the correlation coefficients and their propagation through to autocorrelation lengthscales and further to the estimation of lengthscales associated with

staircases. Instead we view the average of the points such as those represented by the red lines in Figure 2 as ‘characteristic’ lengthscales rather than ones that require precise error determination.

2.1.2 Decorrelation timescales

Water-mass properties and their distribution vary on a range of timescales, from daily to interdecadal frequencies. Constraining this variability is essential to understand whether the ongoing change is a forced response (because of the ongoing warming) or is part of the inherent variability of the climate system, also known as internal variability. Long timeseries are needed to properly separate the internal climate variability from the forced response. Unfortunately, the available $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ measurements available in the Southern Ocean are not enough to provide an answer for the ongoing observed changes.

Fig. 7: De-trended and interpolated $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ time series from the south-eastern Amundsen Sea (73.5°S – 75.5°S; 108°W – 100°W) (in black), overlapped with the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO; in red) and Southern Annular Mode (SAM; in blue) climatic indexes.

To the best of our knowledge, there is only one region in Antarctica which has been systematically sampled for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ for years, the southeastern Amundsen Sea, which data has recently been made publicly available (Hennig et al., 2024). Because there is not enough data to resolve the seasonal cycle, here we estimate yearly averages from all the data available in the upper ocean (<400 m) in the south-eastern Amundsen Sea (73.5°S – 75.5°S; 108°W – 100°W) to some gain insights in the interannual variability. Measurements of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ were carried out in 1994, 2000, 2007, 2009, 2014, 2019 and 2020, which shows an interannual variability with an amplitude of $\sim 0.16\text{‰}$ (Figure 5). Very similar variability is also identified for both temperature and salinity (not shown), pointing to the co-occurrence of warmer, saltier and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -enriched waters. Part of the variability is expected to result from large scale atmospheric patterns such as the Southern Annular Mode (SAM) and the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO). Atmospheric teleconnections impact the saltier and warmer Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) inflow to the continental shelves by, -e.g., modifying the strength of the circumpolar westerly winds which induces meridional Ekman transport into the coastal regions (Dotto et al., 2018).

We performed an autocorrelation analysis on the detrended and interpolated time series of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data, which suggest a correlation timescale of about 5 years, and an anticorrelation peak after 10 years (Figure 6). This autocorrelation suggests some decadal variability, also seen in Figure 5. Unfortunately, the available observations are not enough to suggest any meaningful conclusions nor any correlations between $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and SAM or ENSO climate indexes. The lack of available time-series in the Southern Ocean call for strengthening of the observing system to detect the ongoing and expected changes in the Antarctic ice-shelves and their effect in ocean circulation.

Fig.8: Decorrelation timescales of 5 years and anticorrelation timescales of 10 years computed from the interpolated times series in the south-eastern Amundsen Sea (73.5°S – 75.5°S; 108°W - 100°W).

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2.2 Open Science

The data set used for the decorrelation lengthscales is available in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8226802> (Gebbie et al., 2023) and in GitHub <https://github.com/ggebbie/TMI.jl>

The time series data used for estimating the decorrelation timescales can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.25740/zf704jg7109> (Hennig et al., 2024). This report (also available) represents the methods and the results.

3. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objective (O) of the project indicated in the Description of the Action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica

The results contained in this deliverable will inform the density of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ observations required to observe the parameter completely. The shortest space scale is 100-300 km. Thus, we recommend at least 100km sample spacing to resolve $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ variability. In addition, the surface lengthscales estimated here will help guiding the data inversion planned in this project task. We further recommend high resolution sampling O(20km) to characterise the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signature of eddies in the Southern Ocean. Time series exist that indicate significant $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ temporal variability on multi annual timescales, however there is insufficient temporal resolution to determine dominant timescales. Thus, we recommend collection of data sets of at least monthly resolution to determine temporal timescales in a similar way to what we have done for spatial scales.